

Research Article

Median-Based Unit Weibull (MBUW): A New Variants of Generalized Method of Moments and Percentile Estimators

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This paper introduces a new two-parameter unit Weibull distribution defined on the interval $(0, 1)$. It discusses the methodology for deriving its probability density function (PDF), explores various properties, and presents related functions. Numerous figures illustrate the distribution and demonstrate its effectiveness in fitting a wide range of skewed real data. The parameter estimation process using maximum likelihood estimation (MLE) faced challenges, particularly concerning large variance. To address these issues, the generalized method of moments (GMMs) and percentile estimators are introduced as improved alternatives. The paper elaborates on GMMs, percentile estimators, and new variants of both methods for estimating the parameters of the new distribution, supplemented by illustrative analysis of real data.

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1. Introduction

The Weibull distribution can describe cases with both increasing and decreasing failure rates. But, due to the distribution's inability to adequately represent bathtub or unimodal shapes, many researchers have sought to generalize and transform it in recent decades. Notable contributions include the study [1] on beta-generalized Weibull, study [2] on transmuted Weibull, study [3] on modified Weibull, study [4] on beta Weibull, study [5] on Kumaraswamy Weibull, study [6] on beta modified Weibull, study [7] on exponentiated Weibull, study [8] on truncated Weibull, study [9] on transmuted modified Weibull, and study [10] on extended Weibull.

Numerous distributions have been defined on unit intervals by various authors, including the Johnson SB distribution [11], beta distribution [12], Unit Johnson (SU) distribution [13], Unit Burr-XII [14], Topp-Leone distribution [15], Unit-Gompertz [16], Unit Logistic distribution [17],

Kumaraswamy distribution [18], Unit Burr-III [19], Unit modified Burr-III [20], Unit Gamma distribution [21–24], Unit-Lindley [25], Unit-Weibull [26], and Unit Muth distribution [27]. Recently, Mazucheli et al. [28] proposed a unit Weibull distribution to model data on the unit interval, using real datasets such as maximum flood levels and petroleum reservoir data. They introduced a quantile regression model for this unit Weibull distribution, demonstrating its superiority over competing distributions like the beta, Kumaraswamy, Unit Logistic, Simplex, Unit Gamma, Exponentiated Topp-Leone, and Extended Arcsine distributions, as it provides a closed formula for the quantile function.

In this paper, the author explores a new unit Weibull distribution based on the probability density function (PDF) of the median order statistics from a sample size of three. The discussion focuses on the newly defined two-parameter distribution, the median-based unit Weibull (MBUW), and its basic properties.

The paper is structured into the following sections. Methodology outlines the derivation for obtaining the new distribution and the elaboration on its PDF, cumulative distribution function (CDF), survival function, hazard function, reversed hazard function, and additional properties. New methods for estimating the parameters are discussed such as the generalized method of moments (GMMs) and percentile estimators. The statistics used in these methods are moment-based statistics like in Methods 1 and 2, quantile-based statistics like in Methods 5 and 6, and mixed quantile and moment-based statistics like in Methods 3 and 4, as the log geometric mean is considered the zeroth moment. Results analyze the voter dataset to illustrate how to fit data to different competing distributions and how to apply the

mentioned estimation methods for the MBUW distribution. Discussion clarifies the comparison between methods. Conclusions depict with remarks on the findings and future research directions.

2. Methodology

2.1. Derivation of the MBUW Distribution. Using the PDF of median order statistics of a sample size equal to 3 in equation (1) and the CDF and the PDF of the parent distribution Weibull in equation (2), substitute these functions in equation (1) to give the PDF in equation (3). Both parameters, alpha and beta, are positive.

$$f_{i:n}(z) = \frac{n!}{(i-1)!(n-i)!} \{F(z)\}^{i-1} \{1-F(z)\}^{n-i} f(z), \quad z > 0, \quad (1)$$

$$F(z) = 1 - e^{-(z/\alpha)^\beta}, \quad f(z) = \frac{\beta}{\alpha} \left(\frac{z}{\alpha}\right)^{\beta-1} e^{-(z/\alpha)^\beta}, \quad z > 0, \alpha & \beta > 0, \quad (2)$$

$$f_{2:3}(z) = \frac{6\beta z^{\beta-1}}{\alpha^\beta} \left[1 - e^{((-z)^\beta/(\alpha^\beta))} \right] \left[e^{((-2z)^\beta/(\alpha^\beta))} \right], \quad z > 0, \alpha & \beta > 0. \quad (3)$$

Apply the following transformation $y = e^{-z^\beta}$ on equation (3), and using the Jacobian in equation (4), the PDF of the new MBUW distribution is obtained in equation (5):

$$\frac{dz}{dy} = \frac{1}{\beta} [-\ln(y)]^{(1-\beta)/\beta} \left(\frac{-1}{y}\right), \quad (4)$$

$$f(y) = \frac{6}{\alpha^\beta} \left[1 - y^{(1/(\alpha^\beta))} \right] y^{((2/(\alpha^\beta))-1)}, \quad 0 < y < 1, \alpha > 0, \beta > 0. \quad (5)$$

2.2. Some of the Properties of the New Distribution (MBUW).

The PDF is shown in equation (5). The CDF, survival function, hazard function, reversed hazard function, and quantile function are shown in equations (6)–(10), respectively.

$$F(y) = 3y^{(2/(\alpha^\beta))} - 2y^{(3/(\alpha^\beta))}, \quad 0 < y < 1, \alpha > 0, \beta > 0, \quad (6)$$

$$S(y) = 1 - F(y) = 1 - \left(3y^{(2/(\alpha^\beta))} - 2y^{(3/(\alpha^\beta))} \right), \quad 0 < y < 1, \alpha > 0, \beta > 0, \quad (7)$$

$$h(y) = \frac{f(y)}{S(y)} = \frac{(6/(\alpha^\beta)) \left(1 - y^{(1/(\alpha^\beta))} \right) y^{((2/(\alpha^\beta))-1)}}{1 - \left(3y^{(2/(\alpha^\beta))} - 2y^{(3/(\alpha^\beta))} \right)}, \quad 0 < y < 1, \alpha > 0, \beta > 0, \quad (8)$$

$$rh(y) = \frac{f(y)}{F(y)} = \frac{(6/(\alpha^\beta))(1 - y^{(1/(\alpha^\beta))})y^{((2/(\alpha^\beta))-1)}}{3y^{(2/(\alpha^\beta))} - 2y^{(3/(\alpha^\beta))}}, \quad 0 < y < 1, \alpha > 0, \beta > 0. \tag{9}$$

The inverse of the CDF is used to obtain y ; the real root of this 3rd polynomial function is shown in equation (10):

$$y = F^{-1}(y) = \left\{ -0.5 \left(\cos \left[\frac{\cos^{-1}(1 - 2u)}{3} \right] - \sqrt{3} \sin \left[\frac{\cos^{-1}(1 - 2u)}{3} \right] \right) + 0.5 \right\}^{\alpha^\beta}. \tag{10}$$

In Figures 1, 2, 3, 4, for a random variable y distributed as MBUW, detailed depictions of the PDF, CDF, hazard rate function, and survival functions for specific alpha values (0.5, 1, 1.5, 2.5, 4.5) and beta values (0.6, 3.5) are shown. These comprehensive representations are designed to provide clarity and depth, making it easier to grasp the underlying concepts.

To generate random variable y distributed as MBUW:

1. Generate a uniform random variable (0, 1): $u \sim \text{uniform}(0, 1)$
2. Choose alpha and beta levels
3. Substitute the above values of u (0, 1) and the chosen alpha and beta in the quantile function to obtain y distributed as $y \sim \text{MBUW}(\alpha, \beta)$

The raw moments of the distribution are expressed in equation (11).

$$E(y^r) = \frac{6}{(2 + r\alpha^\beta)(3 + r\alpha^\beta)} = \int_0^1 y^r \frac{6}{\alpha^\beta} [1 - y^{(1/(\alpha^\beta))}] y^{((2/(\alpha^\beta))-1)} dy. \tag{11}$$

The r th incomplete moment is expressed in equation (12).

$$E(y^r | y < t) = \int_0^t y^r \frac{6}{\alpha^\beta} [1 - y^{(1/(\alpha^\beta))}] y^{((2/(\alpha^\beta))-1)} dy = \frac{6y^{(2/(\alpha^\beta))+r}}{(2 + r\alpha^\beta)} - \frac{6y^{(3/(\alpha^\beta))+r}}{(3 + r\alpha^\beta)}. \tag{12}$$

3. Methods of Estimations

3.1. GMMs

3.1.1. The First and Second Raw Moments (Method 1). The GMM has been developed by various authors, including Benson [29] and the United States Water Resources Council [30, 31], as well as Bobé [32], Hoshi and Burges [33], Rao [34], Ashkar and Bobé [35, 36], and Bobe and Ashkar [37]. These authors applied the well-known four methods of GMM to the Log Pearson Type 3 (LP) distribution. However, these methods can be utilized for any distribution and are not limited to the LP distribution. As demonstrated by Shenton and Bowman [38], maximum likelihood (ML) estimators are, in fact, moment estimators when dealing with the LP distribution. Additionally, Ashkar et al. [39] introduced GMMs for estimating the parameters of the generalized gamma distribution. GMMs utilize the raw moments of

a distribution. The core principle of the method involves equating the sample moments with the population moments.

Steps of the algorithm are as follows:

The noncentral sample moments of order r for a given sample y_1, y_2, \dots, y_N are defined as in equation $m'_r(y) = (1/N) \sum_{i=1}^r y_i^r$. For a distribution, the noncentral population moment has the following formulae $\mu'_r = E(y^r) = 6/(2 + r\alpha^\beta)(3 + r\alpha^\beta)$. Equating the sample moment and the population moment yields $m'_r(y) = \mu'_r$. For the first and second order $m'_1(y) = \mu'_1$ and $m'_2(y) = \mu'_2$, respectively. Applying this to MBUW, $1/N \sum_{i=1}^r y = \bar{y} = 6/(2 + \alpha^\beta)(3 + \alpha^\beta)$, let's call this Mom_1 or μ'_1 and the $1/N \sum_{i=1}^r y^2 = 6/(2 + 2\alpha^\beta)(3 + 2\alpha^\beta)$ and let us call this Mom_2 or μ'_2 . Differentiating both μ'_1 and μ'_2 with respect to both parameters yield system of equations (13)–(16) to be solved numerically using the Levenberg–Marquardt (LM) algorithm as in equation (17).

FIGURE 1: PDF of (MBUW) distribution, alpha (0.5, 1, 1.5, 2.5, 4.5) and beta (0.6, 3.5).

FIGURE 2: CDF of (MBUW) distribution, alpha (0.5, 1, 1.5, 2.4, 4.5) and beta (0.6, 3.5).

FIGURE 3: Survival function of (MBUW) distribution, alpha (0.5, 1, 1.5, 2.5, 4.5) and beta (0.6, 3.6).

FIGURE 4: Hazard rate function of (MBUW) distribution, alpha (0.5, 1, 1.5, 2.5, 4.5) and beta (0.6, 3.5).

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha} \left[\frac{6}{(2 + \alpha^\beta)(3 + \alpha^\beta)} \right] = -6(6 + 5\alpha^\beta + \alpha^{2\beta})^{-2} (5\beta\alpha^{\beta-1} + 2\beta\alpha^{2\beta-1}), \quad (13)$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \beta} \left[\frac{6}{(2 + \alpha^\beta)(3 + \alpha^\beta)} \right] = -6(6 + 5\alpha^\beta + \alpha^{2\beta})^{-2} (5\alpha^\beta \ln(\alpha) + 2\alpha^{2\beta} \ln(\alpha)), \quad (14)$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha} \left[\frac{6}{(2 + 2\alpha^\beta)(3 + 2\alpha^\beta)} \right] = -6(6 + 10\alpha^\beta + 4\alpha^{2\beta})^{-2} (10\beta\alpha^{\beta-1} + 8\beta\alpha^{2\beta-1}), \quad (15)$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \beta} \left[\frac{6}{(2 + 2\alpha^\beta)(3 + 2\alpha^\beta)} \right] = -6(6 + 10\alpha^\beta + 4\alpha^{2\beta})^{-2} (10\alpha^\beta \ln(\alpha) + 8\alpha^{2\beta} \ln(\alpha)), \quad (16)$$

$$\theta^{(a+1)} = \theta^{(a)} + [J'(\theta^{(a)})J(\theta^{(a)}) + \lambda^{(a)}I^{(a)}]^{-1} [J'(\theta^{(a)})](y - f(\theta^{(a)})), \quad (17)$$

where $J = \begin{bmatrix} (\partial/\partial\alpha)\mu'_1 & (\partial/\partial\beta)\mu'_1 \\ (\partial/\partial\alpha)\mu'_2 & (\partial/\partial\beta)\mu'_2 \end{bmatrix}$ and $(y - f(\theta^{(a)})) = \begin{bmatrix} m'_1 - \mu'_1 \\ m'_2 - \mu'_2 \end{bmatrix}$, where $\theta^{(a)} = \begin{bmatrix} \alpha^{(a)} \\ \beta^{(a)} \end{bmatrix}$

$\theta^{(a)}$ is the parameter used in the first iteration, which is the initial guess, and then they are updated according to the sum of squares of errors. The LM algorithm is an iterative algorithm. $J'(\theta^{(a)})$ is the Jacobian function which is the first derivative of the objective function evaluated at the initial guess $\theta^{(a)}$. $\lambda^{(a)}$ is a damping factor that adjusts the step size in each iteration direction; the starting value usually is 0.001, and according to the sum of squares errors (SSE) in each iteration this, damping factor is adjusted:

$SSE^{(a+1)} \geq SSE^{(a)}$ so update: $\lambda_{\text{updated}} = 10 * \lambda_{\text{old}}$ and $SSE^{(a+1)} < SSE^{(a)}$ so update: $\lambda_{\text{updated}} = 1/10 * \lambda_{\text{old}}$. $f(\theta^{(a)})$ is the objective function (noncentral population moment, first and second order) evaluated at the initial guess. y is the noncentral sample moments, the first and second order.

Steps of the LM algorithm are as follows:

1. Start with the initial guess of parameters (alpha and beta).
2. Substitute these values in the objective function and the Jacobian.
3. Choose the damping factor, say lambda = 0.001.
4. Substitute in equation (LM equation (17)) to get the new parameters.
5. Calculate the SSE at these parameters and compare this SSE value with the previous one when using initial parameters to adjust for the damping factor.
6. Update the damping factor accordingly as previously explained.
7. Start a new iteration with the new parameters and the new updated damping factor, that is, apply the previous steps many times until convergence is achieved or a prespecified number of iterations is approached.

Using the Taylor series expansion of the $g_1(\theta) = \mu'_1$ and $g_2(\theta) = \mu'_2$ around the θ_0 gives $g(\hat{\theta}) = g(\theta_0) + (\hat{\theta} - \theta_0)g'(\theta_0)$ therefore, the delta method can be applied. Taking the variance on both sides yields $\text{var}[g(\hat{\theta})] = [g'(\theta_0)]\text{var}(\hat{\theta})[g'(\theta_0)]^T$ where $g'(\theta_0) = (\partial g(\theta_0)/\partial \theta_0)|_{\theta_0 = \hat{\theta}}$ which is the Jacobian matrix in the ML algorithm.

Hence, $\text{var}(\hat{\theta}) = [[g'(\theta_0)]^T (\text{var}[g(\hat{\theta})])^{-1} g'(\theta_0)]^{-1}$ & $\text{var}[g(\hat{\theta})] = \begin{bmatrix} \text{var}(\mu'_1) & \text{cov}(\mu'_1, \mu'_2) \\ \text{cov}(\mu'_2, \mu'_1) & \text{var}(\mu'_2) \end{bmatrix}$ and $\text{var}(\mu'_r) = (\mu'_{2r} - (\mu'_r)^2)/n$ and $\text{cov}(\mu'_r, \mu'_q) = (\mu'_{r+q} - \mu'_r \mu'_q)/n$ according to [40].

This matrix $[g'(\theta_0)]^T (\text{var}[g(\hat{\theta})])^{-1} g'(\theta_0)$ may have a high condition number that inflates the $\text{var}(\hat{\theta})$. To combat this, an appropriate regularization factor can be added to matrix like this $[[g'(\theta_0)]^T (\text{var}[g(\hat{\theta})])^{-1} g'(\theta_0) + \lambda I]^{-1}$, where $\lambda = (\lambda_{\max} - C^* \lambda_{\min})/C^* - 1$ such that λ_{\max} is the maximum eigenvalue of the $[g'(\theta_0)]^T (\text{var}[g(\hat{\theta})])^{-1} g'(\theta_0)$ and λ_{\min} is the minimum eigenvalue for the same matrix. The C^* is the desired condition number. The desired value of this number is from 5 to 10.

The value of this quantity: $[J'(\theta^{(a)})J(\theta^{(a)}) + \lambda^{(a)}I^{(a)}]^{-1}$ can be considered a good approximation to the variance-covariance matrix of the estimated parameters $\hat{\theta}$. Using the delta method and squaring the Jacobian matrix is applied to derive the standard errors for the function of the estimated parameters. See Appendix A for the variance-covariance of the first and second moments.

Other noncentral raw moments can be used in the following variants of the generalized method of moments.

3.1.2. The Third and the Fourth Raw Moments (Method 2). Equating $m'_3(y) = \mu'_3$ and $m'_4(y) = \mu'_4$ gives the following system of equations (18)–(21). Let us call the functions to be differentiated: Mom_3 or μ'_3 for (18) and (19) and Mom_4 or μ'_4 for (20) and (21).

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha} \left[\frac{6}{(2 + 3\alpha^\beta)(3 + 3\alpha^\beta)} \right] = -6(6 + 15\alpha^\beta + 9\alpha^{2\beta})^{-2} (15\beta\alpha^{\beta-1} + 18\beta\alpha^{2\beta-1}), \tag{18}$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \beta} \left[\frac{6}{(2 + 3\alpha^\beta)(3 + 3\alpha^\beta)} \right] = -6(6 + 15\alpha^\beta + 9\alpha^{2\beta})^{-2} (15\alpha^\beta \ln(\alpha) + 18\alpha^{2\beta} \ln(\alpha)), \tag{19}$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha} \left[\frac{6}{(2 + 4\alpha^\beta)(3 + 4\alpha^\beta)} \right] = -6(6 + 20\alpha^\beta + 16\alpha^{2\beta})^{-2} (20\beta\alpha^{\beta-1} + 32\beta\alpha^{2\beta-1}), \tag{20}$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \beta} \left[\frac{6}{(2 + 4\alpha^\beta)(3 + 4\alpha^\beta)} \right] = -6(6 + 20\alpha^\beta + 16\alpha^{2\beta})^{-2} (20\alpha^\beta \ln(\alpha) + 32\alpha^{2\beta} \ln(\alpha)). \tag{21}$$

Apply the LM algorithm where the Jacobian matrix is

$$\begin{bmatrix} (\partial/\partial\alpha)\mu'_3 & (\partial/\partial\beta)\mu'_3 \\ (\partial/\partial\alpha)\mu'_4 & (\partial/\partial\beta)\mu'_4 \end{bmatrix}, (y - f(\theta^{(a)})) = \begin{bmatrix} m'_3 - \mu'_3 \\ m'_4 - \mu'_4 \end{bmatrix}$$

To get estimation for var ($\hat{\theta}$), the same procedure is followed as in method one. See Appendix A for the variance-covariance of the third and fourth moments.

3.1.3. *Skewness Defined as Quartile and Log of the Geometric Mean (Method 3)*. Population skewness can be defined in equation (22) using the parametric quantile function defined in equation (10) as

$$S_{\text{pop}} = \frac{Q(3/4) - 2Q(2/4) + Q(1/4)}{Q(3/4) - Q(1/4)}, \tag{22}$$

while the sample skewness is obtained from the sample by the empirical quantiles as in equation (23).

$$S_{\text{sample}} = \frac{Q(3/4) - 2Q(2/4) + Q(1/4)}{Q(3/4) - Q(1/4)}. \tag{23}$$

Equate equations (22) and (23), then differentiate equation (22) with respect to both parameters and apply the LM algorithm in the same manner as in Methods 1 and 2.

Transformation of the observations into the log scale is used to obtain the log of the geometric mean which gives the following equation (24) (z is the log of the geometric mean or zero raw moment, i.e., z_{sample} , which is the sample log geometric mean)

$$z_{\text{sample}} = \ln \prod_{i=1}^n y_i^{(1/n)} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \ln y_i = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{n} (\ln y_i) = \sum_{i=1}^n \ln y_i^{(1/n)}. \tag{24}$$

Getting the expectation of the log of the observations gives the population log geometric mean, as in equation (25).

$$Z_{\text{pop}} = E\{\ln y_i\} = \int_0^1 (\ln y_i) f_Y(y) dy = \frac{-5}{6} \alpha^\beta. \tag{25}$$

Equating equation (24) with equation (25), differentiate equation (25) with respect to both parameters and apply the LM algorithm as in Methods 1 and 2. In other words, we obtain the following system of equations (26)–(29)

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha} [S_{\text{pop}}] = \frac{[Q'(3/4) - 2Q'(2/4) + Q'(1/4)][Q(3/4) - Q(1/4)] - [Q(3/4) - 2Q(2/4) + Q(1/4)][Q'(3/4) - Q'(1/4)]}{[Q(3/4) - Q(1/4)]^2}, \tag{26}$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \beta} [S_{\text{pop}}] = \frac{[Q'(3/4) - 2Q'(2/4) + Q'(1/4)][Q(3/4) - Q(1/4)] - [Q(3/4) - 2Q(2/4) + Q(1/4)][Q'(3/4) - Q'(1/4)]}{[Q(3/4) - Q(1/4)]^2}, \tag{27}$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha} [Z_{\text{pop}}] = \frac{-5}{6} \beta \alpha^{\beta-1}, \tag{28}$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \beta} [Z_{\text{pop}}] = \frac{-5}{6} \alpha^\beta \ln \alpha. \tag{29}$$

The Jacobian matrix is $\begin{bmatrix} (\partial/\partial\alpha)S_{\text{pop}} & (\partial/\partial\beta)S_{\text{pop}} \\ (\partial/\partial\alpha)Z_{\text{pop}} & (\partial/\partial\beta)Z_{\text{pop}} \end{bmatrix}$, $(y - f(\theta^{(a)})) = [S_{\text{sample}} - (Q(3/4) - 2Q(2/4) + Q(1/4))/(Q(3/4) - Q(1/4))z_{\text{sample}} - ((-5)/6)\alpha^\beta]$

To get estimation for var ($\hat{\theta}$) use var ($\hat{\theta}$) = $[J'(\theta^{(a)})J(\theta^{(a)}) + \lambda^{(a)}I^{(a)}]^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} \text{var}(\beta) & \text{cov}(\alpha, \beta) \\ \text{cov}(\alpha, \beta) & \text{var}(\alpha) \end{bmatrix}$ then apply the delta method; var [$g(\hat{\theta})$] = [$g'(\theta_0)$]var ($\hat{\theta}$)

$[g'(\theta_0)]^T$ to get estimation of the variance of the function of the parameter. Because in the previous two methods using the moments, the covariance between two statistics comes from them being functions of a common underlying random vector like the moments. In this method, the skewness and log of the geometric mean are defined in terms of estimated parameters, no common moments or quantiles between both statistics. So in this method, the matrix obtained from the LM algorithm can be a good approximation to the $\text{var}(\hat{\theta})$ and applying the delta method can give approximation to $\text{var}[g(\hat{\theta})]$, the covariance matrix for the functions or statistics of the estimated parameters. Another approach to estimate the variance of the estimated parameter is to use the

$$S = \frac{Q(9/10) - 2Q(1/2) + Q(1/10)}{Q(9/10) - Q(1/10)}, \quad (30)$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha} [S_{\text{pop}}] = \frac{[Q'(9/10) - 2Q'(1/2) + Q'(1/10)][Q(9/10) - Q(1/10)] - [Q(9/10) - 2Q(1/2) + Q(1/10)][Q'(9/10) - Q'(1/10)]}{[Q(9/10) - Q(1/10)]^2}, \quad (31)$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \beta} [S_{\text{pop}}] = \frac{[Q'(9/10) - 2Q'(1/2) + Q'(1/10)][Q(9/10) - Q(1/10)] - [Q(9/10) - 2Q(1/2) + Q(1/10)][Q'(9/10) - Q'(1/10)]}{[Q(9/10) - Q(1/10)]^2}, \quad (32)$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha} [Z_{\text{pop}}] = \frac{-5}{6} \beta \alpha^{\beta-1}, \quad (33)$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \beta} [Z_{\text{pop}}] = \frac{-5}{6} \alpha^\beta \ln \alpha. \quad (34)$$

The Jacobian matrix is $\begin{bmatrix} (\partial/\partial \alpha)S_{\text{pop}} & (\partial/\partial \beta)S_{\text{pop}} \\ (\partial/\partial \alpha)Z_{\text{pop}} & (\partial/\partial \beta)Z_{\text{pop}} \end{bmatrix}$, $(y - f(\theta^{(a)})) = \begin{bmatrix} S_{\text{sample}} - (Q(9/10) - 2Q(1/2) + Q(1/10))/(Q(9/10) - Q(1/10)) \\ Z_{\text{sample}} - ((-5)/6)\alpha^\beta \end{bmatrix}$

For $\text{var}(\hat{\theta})$ and $\text{var}[g(\hat{\theta})]$, the same is applicable as in Method 4.

3.1.5. Method of Percentiles (Method 5). The use of percentiles for estimation has a longstanding and proven track

resampling bootstrap procedure or simulation which can estimate the statistics variance–covariance matrix which can then be used as described in Methods 1 and 2 to estimate the $\text{var}(\hat{\theta})$.

3.1.4. Skewness Defined as Decile and the Log of the Geometric Mean (Method 4). Method 4 is the same as Method 3, with the difference being the definition of the sample and population skewness. In Method 4, the skewness is defined as in equation (30) and follows the steps as in Method 3, resulting in equations (31)–(34).

record. Numerous authors have effectively employed this method, demonstrating that it is at least as efficient, if not more so, than ML estimation (MLE) and least squares [41–44].

The percentile method used in this paper is applied to the 25th and 75th percentiles. The MBUW has the quantile or the percentile function defined in equation (10). Substitute for $u=0.25$ and $u=0.75$ to obtain population 25th and 75th percentiles as shown in equations (35) and (36):

$$y_{25} = \left\{ -0.5 \left(\cos \left[\frac{\cos^{-1}(1 - 2 * 0.25)}{3} \right] - \sqrt{3} \sin \left[\frac{\cos^{-1}(1 - 2 * 0.25)}{3} \right] \right) + 0.5 \right\}^{\alpha^\beta}, \quad \text{i.e. } y_{25} = c_{25}^{\alpha^\beta}, \quad (35)$$

$$y_{75} = \left\{ -0.5 \left(\cos \left[\frac{\cos^{-1}(1 - 2 * 0.75)}{3} \right] - \sqrt{3} \sin \left[\frac{\cos^{-1}(1 - 2 * 0.75)}{3} \right] \right) + 0.5 \right\}^{\alpha^\beta}, \quad \text{i.e. } y_{75} = c_{75}^{\alpha^\beta}, \quad (36)$$

where $c_u = \{-0.5(\cos[\cos^{-1}(1 - 2u)/3] - \sqrt{3} \sin[\cos^{-1}(1 - 2u)/3]) + 0.5\}$

Differentiating both equations (35) and (36) with respect to both parameters gives (37)–(40):

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha} y_{25} = c_{25}^{\alpha\beta} [\ln(c_{25})] \beta \alpha^{\beta-1}, \tag{37}$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \beta} y_{25} = c_{25}^{\alpha\beta} [\ln(c_{25})] (\alpha^\beta) [\ln(\alpha)], \tag{38}$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha} y_{75} = c_{75}^{\alpha\beta} [\ln(c_{75})] \beta \alpha^{\beta-1}, \tag{39}$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \beta} y_{75} = c_{75}^{\alpha\beta} [\ln(c_{75})] (\alpha^\beta) [\ln(\alpha)]. \tag{40}$$

The Jacobian matrix is $\begin{bmatrix} \partial/(\partial\alpha)y_{25} & \partial/(\partial\beta)y_{25} \\ \partial/(\partial\alpha)y_{75} & \partial/(\partial\beta)y_{75} \end{bmatrix}$ and $(y - f(\theta^{(a)})) = \begin{bmatrix} y_{25} - c_{25}^{\alpha\beta} \\ y_{75} - c_{75}^{\alpha\beta} \end{bmatrix}$ then apply LM algorithm.

Where $y_{25} = Q(1/4)$ and $y_{75} = Q(3/4)$ are the empirical sample percentiles. Any percentiles can be used. The most common to use are the 25th and 75th percentiles. Reference [45] used many different combinations of percentiles and assessed the outcome for each combination. We can define $g_1(\theta) = \varphi_1(Q)$ and $g_2(\theta) = \varphi_2(Q)$. Estimating the $\text{var}(\hat{\theta})$ can be achieved by applying the same procedure as in

Methods 1 and 2. Because both statistics in Method 5 have a common random vector in their definition which is the vector of quantiles. And each quantile has a specific variance and different quantiles have covariance. First, calculate the matrix of $\text{var}[g(\hat{\theta})] = \varphi'(\mathbf{Q})\text{var}(\hat{\mathbf{Q}})[\varphi'(\mathbf{Q})]^T$ as shown below:

$$\varphi'(\mathbf{Q}) = \begin{bmatrix} (\partial\varphi_1(Q))/(\partial Q(1/4)) & (\partial\varphi_1(Q))/(\partial Q(3/4)) \\ (\partial\varphi_2(Q))/(\partial Q(1/4)) & (\partial\varphi_2(Q))/(\partial Q(3/4)) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \text{ so}$$

$$\text{var}[g(\hat{\theta})] = \varphi'(\mathbf{Q})\text{var}(\hat{\mathbf{Q}})[\varphi'(\mathbf{Q})]^T = \text{var}(\hat{\mathbf{Q}}).$$

$\text{var}[\hat{Q}(1/4)] = (p(1-p)/nf^2(\hat{Q}(p)))$ where $p = 0.25$ and $f(\hat{Q}(p))$ is the PDF at estimated quantile, the same is true for $\text{var}[\hat{Q}(3/4)]$ where $p = 0.75$. The $\text{cov}[\hat{Q}(1/4), \hat{Q}(3/4)] = (\min(0.25, 0.75) - (0.25)(0.75)/nf(\hat{Q}(0.25))f(\hat{Q}(0.75)))$.

Then apply: $\text{var}(\hat{\theta}) = [[g'(\theta_0)]^T (\text{var}[g(\hat{\theta})])^{-1} g'(\theta_0)]^{-1}$ as in method 1, where $g'(\theta_0) = (\partial g(\theta_0)/\partial \theta_0)|_{\theta_0=\hat{\theta}}$

3.1.6. Galton Skewness and Moors Kurtosis Defined Using Octiles (Method 6). Galton defined skewness in equation (41) as

$$S_{\text{Galton-pop}} = \frac{Q(6/8) - 2Q(4/8) + Q(2/8)}{Q(6/8) - Q(2/8)} = \frac{Q(3/4) - 2Q(2/4) + Q(1/4)}{Q(3/4) - Q(1/4)}. \tag{41}$$

Moors defined kurtosis in equation (42) as

$$K_{\text{Moors-pop}} = \frac{Q(7/8) - Q(5/8) + Q(3/8) - Q(1/8)}{Q(6/8) - Q(2/8)}. \tag{42}$$

Population skewness and kurtosis are defined using the parametric quantile function defined in equation (10), while

the sample skewness and sample kurtosis are defined using the same equations but utilizing the empirical quantiles from the observations. The system of equations is defined as follows in equations (43)–(46).

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha} [S_{\text{Galton-pop}}] = \frac{[Q'(6/8) - 2Q'(4/8) + Q'(2/8)][Q(6/8) - Q(2/8)] - [Q(6/8) - 2Q(4/8) + Q(2/8)][Q'(6/8) - Q'(2/8)]}{[Q(6/8) - Q(2/8)]^2}, \tag{43}$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \beta} [S_{\text{Galton-pop}}] = \frac{[Q'(6/8) - 2Q'(4/8) + Q'(2/8)][Q(6/8) - Q(2/8)] - [Q(6/8) - 2Q(4/8) + Q(2/8)][Q'(6/8) - Q'(2/8)]}{[Q(6/8) - Q(2/8)]^2}, \tag{44}$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha} [K_{\text{Moors-pop}}] = \frac{[Q'(7/8) - Q'(5/8) + Q'(3/8) - Q'(1/8)][Q(6/8) - Q(2/8)] - [Q(7/8) - Q(5/8) + Q(3/8) - Q(1/8)][Q'(6/8) - Q'(2/8)]}{[Q(6/8) - Q(2/8)]^2}, \tag{45}$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \beta} [K_{\text{Moors-pop}}] = \frac{[Q'(7/8) - Q'(5/8) + Q'(3/8) - Q'(1/8)][Q(6/8) - Q(2/8)] - [Q(7/8) - Q(5/8) + Q(3/8) - Q(1/8)][Q'(6/8) - Q'(2/8)]}{[Q(6/8) - Q(2/8)]^2}. \tag{46}$$

The Jacobian matrix is $\begin{bmatrix} (\partial/\partial\alpha)S_{\text{Galton-pop}} & (\partial/\partial\beta)S_{\text{Galton-pop}} \\ (\partial/\partial\alpha)K_{\text{Moors-pop}} & (\partial/\partial\beta)K_{\text{Moors-pop}} \end{bmatrix}$, $(y - f(\theta^{(a)})) = \begin{bmatrix} S_{\text{Galton-sample}} - (Q(6/8) - 2Q(4/8) + Q(2/8))/(Q(6/8) - Q(2/8)) \\ K_{\text{Moors-sample}} - (Q(7/8) - Q(5/8) + Q(3/8) - Q(1/8))/(Q(6/8) - Q(2/8)) \end{bmatrix}$.

To obtain the $\text{var}(\hat{\theta})$ of this method, the same procedure as in method 5 can be used but with some different manipulations. First, estimating the $\text{var}[g(\hat{\theta})]$ using the multivariate delta method. Because skewness and kurtosis are functions of the same quantiles, these quantiles can be

collected in one vector. Let's define the g matrix in terms of quantiles $g_1(\theta) = \varphi_1(Q)$ and $g_2(\theta) = \varphi_2(Q)$. Construct $g'_1(\theta) = \varphi'_1(Q)$ and $g'_2(\theta) = \varphi'_2(Q)$, these are the first derivatives of the quantiles with respect to each quantile arranged in a matrix of size 2 by 7 as shown below, where N_1

and D_1 denote the numerator and denominator of skewness, respectively. The N_2 and D_2 denote the numerator and denominator of kurtosis, respectively, as shown in equation (47)

$$\begin{bmatrix} \frac{\varphi'_1(Q)}{Q(1/8)} & \frac{\varphi'_1(Q)}{Q(2/8)} & \frac{\varphi'_1(Q)}{Q(3/8)} & \frac{\varphi'_1(Q)}{Q(4/8)} & \frac{\varphi'_1(Q)}{Q(5/8)} & \frac{\varphi'_1(Q)}{Q(6/8)} & \frac{\varphi'_1(Q)}{Q(7/8)} \\ \frac{\varphi'_2(Q)}{Q(1/8)} & \frac{\varphi'_2(Q)}{Q(2/8)} & \frac{\varphi'_2(Q)}{Q(3/8)} & \frac{\varphi'_2(Q)}{Q(4/8)} & \frac{\varphi'_2(Q)}{Q(5/8)} & \frac{\varphi'_2(Q)}{Q(6/8)} & \frac{\varphi'_2(Q)}{Q(7/8)} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} & \frac{D_1 + N_1}{D_1^2} & \mathbf{0} & \frac{-2}{D_1} & \mathbf{0} & \frac{D_1 - N_1}{D_1^2} & \mathbf{0} \\ \frac{-1}{D_2} & \frac{N_2}{D_2^2} & \frac{1}{D_2} & \mathbf{0} & \frac{-1}{D_2} & \frac{-N_2}{D_2^2} & \frac{1}{D_2} \end{bmatrix}. \tag{47}$$

Let us call this matrix: $\varphi'(\hat{Q}) = [\varphi'_1(\hat{Q}) \varphi'_2(\hat{Q})]$ so $\mathbf{var}[g(\hat{\theta})] = \varphi'(\hat{Q}) \mathbf{var}(\hat{Q}) [\varphi'(\hat{Q})]^T$.

the variances of the quantiles, and the off-diagonals are the covariance between each pair of quantiles. See Appendix for construction of this matrix, as shown in equations (48) and (49)

Where $\mathbf{var}(\hat{Q})$ is the variance-covariance matrix of quantiles arranged into a matrix of 7 by 7, the diagonals are

$$\mathbf{var}[\hat{Q}(1/8)] = \frac{p(1-p)}{nf^2(\hat{Q}(p))}, \text{ where } p = 0.125 \text{ and } f(\hat{Q}(p)), \tag{48}$$

$$\mathbf{cov}[\hat{Q}(1/8), \hat{Q}(7/8)] = \frac{\min(0.125, 0.875) - (0.125)(0.875)}{nf(\hat{Q}(0.125))f(\hat{Q}(0.875))}, \tag{49}$$

$\mathbf{var}[g(\hat{\theta})]$ is a matrix of size 2 by 2 and can be used to estimate $\mathbf{var}(\hat{\theta})$ as previously discussed in other methods.

3.2. MLE. Let us observe y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n as a random sample from the MBUW distribution with parameters α, β . The PDF is defined in equation (5). The likelihood function and the log-likelihood function are defined in equations (50) and (51), respectively:

$$L(\alpha, \beta; y) = \left(\frac{6}{\alpha^\beta}\right)^n \prod_{i=1}^n \left[1 - y_i^{(1/(\alpha^\beta))}\right] \prod_{i=1}^n y_i^{((2/(\alpha^\beta))-1)}, \quad 0 < y < 1, \alpha \& \beta > 0, \tag{50}$$

$$l(\alpha, \beta; y) = n \ln(6) - n\beta \ln(\alpha) + \sum_{i=1}^n \ln\left[1 - y_i^{(1/(\alpha^\beta))}\right] + \left(\frac{2}{\alpha^\beta} - 1\right) \sum_{i=1}^n \ln(y_i). \tag{51}$$

The ML equations are the first derivative of the log-likelihood function concerning each parameter as defined in equations (52) and (53):

$$\frac{\partial l(\alpha, \beta; y)}{\partial \alpha} = \frac{-\beta n}{\alpha} + \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{-y_i^{(1/(\alpha^\beta))} (\ln[y_i]) (-\beta \alpha^{-\beta-1})}{1 - y_i^{(1/(\alpha^\beta))}} - 2\beta \alpha^{-\beta-1} \sum_{i=1}^n \ln(y_i), \tag{52}$$

$$\frac{\partial l(\alpha, \beta; y)}{\partial \beta} = -n \ln \alpha + \alpha^{-\beta} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{y_i^{(1/(\alpha^\beta))} \ln[\alpha] \ln[y]}{1 - y_i^{(1/(\alpha^\beta))}} - 2\alpha^{-\beta} [\ln \alpha] \sum_{i=1}^n \ln(y_i). \tag{53}$$

The system of nonlinear equations $(dl(\alpha, \beta; y)/d\alpha) = 0$ and $(dl(\alpha, \beta; y)/d\beta) = 0$ are solved numerically using optimization algorithms like the Quasi-Newton method or Nelder–Mead algorithm to obtain estimators for both parameters α and β . The expected information matrix J_y is the negative expected value of the second derivative of the log-likelihood evaluated at the estimated parameter. Under some regularity conditions and with a large sample size, the inverse of this information matrix is the variance of the estimated parameter. This estimator is approximately normally distributed with equation (54)

$$\sqrt{n} \left(\begin{bmatrix} \alpha \\ \beta \end{bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\alpha} \\ \hat{\beta} \end{bmatrix} \right) \sim N(0, J_y^{-1}). \tag{54}$$

This is used to construct an approximate confidence interval for the parameter in the form of $\hat{\alpha} \pm z_{1-\gamma/2} se(\hat{\alpha})$. SE is the square root of the diagonal of the inverse of the expected information matrix. $z_{1-\gamma/2}$ is the quantile of the standard normal distribution.

4. Results

4.1. Real Data Analysis. The OECD is used. The data are available at <https://stats.oecd.org/index.aspx?DataSetCode=BLI>.

Voter Turnout dataset: This dataset evaluates the percentage of eligible and qualified individuals who cast their votes in elections, reflecting the level of democracy in the country. The dataset is 0.92, 0.76, 0.88, 0.68, 0.47, 0.53, 0.66, 0.62, 0.85, 0.64, 0.69, 0.75, 0.76, 0.58, 0.70, 0.81, 0.63, 0.67, 0.73, 0.53, 0.77, 0.55, 0.57, 0.90, 0.63, 0.79, 0.82, 0.78, 0.68, 0.49, 0.66, 0.53, 0.72, 0.87, 0.45, 0.86, 0.68, 0.65.

4.2. MLE. The analysis of the dataset involves fitting the beta distribution, Kumaraswamy distribution, MBUW distribution, and median-based unit Rayleigh (MBUR) distribution. These distributions are compared using several criteria: negative log-likelihood (nLL), Akaike Information Criterion (AIC), corrected AIC (CAIC), and Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC). Additionally, the Kolmogorov–Smirnov (K-S) test is conducted, and its p value is reported in relation to the null hypothesis (H_0), which states that the dataset follows the tested distribution. If the data does not conform to the distribution, the null hypothesis is rejected. MLE is applied to fit the four distributions using the Nelder–Mead algorithm in MATLAB. Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics, while Figure 5 displays the boxplot for the voter dataset.

These are the PDFs of the distributions used in the analysis.

1. Beta Distribution: $f(y; \alpha, \beta) = (\Gamma(\alpha + \beta) / (\Gamma(\alpha)\Gamma(\beta))) y^{\alpha-1} (1 - y)^{\beta-1}, 0 < y < 1, \alpha > 0, \beta > 0$
2. Kumaraswamy Distribution: $f(y; \alpha, \beta) = \alpha\beta y^{\alpha-1} (1 - y^\alpha)^{\beta-1}, 0 < y < 1, \alpha > 0, \beta > 0$

3. Median-Based Unit Rayleigh: $f(y; \alpha) = (6/\alpha^2) [1 - y^{(1/\alpha^2)}] y^{(2/\alpha^2-1)}, 0 < y < 1, \alpha > 0$

Comparison tools as shown in equations (55)–(58) are: (k) is the number of parameters while (n) is the number of observations.

$$AIC = -2MLL + 2k,$$

$$CAIC = -2MLL + \frac{2kn}{n - k - 1}, \tag{55}$$

$$BIC = -2MLL + k \log(n),$$

$$KS - \text{test} = \text{Sup}_n |F_n - F|,$$

$$F_n = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n I_{x_i < x^*} \tag{56}$$

$$CVM - \text{test} = \frac{1}{12n} + \sum_{i=1}^n \left\{ F(x_i) - \frac{2i-1}{2n} \right\}^2, \tag{57}$$

$$AD - \text{test} = -n - \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{2i-1}{n} \right) \{ \log[F(x_i)] + \log[1 - F(x_{n-i+1})] \}. \tag{58}$$

In Table 1, the descriptive analysis reveals that the voter dataset exhibits significant negative skewness, characterized by a tail on the left side. This dataset is platykurtic, demonstrating negative excess kurtosis (kurtosis less than 3, indicating a thinner tail). Figure 5 shows the boxplot for the dataset.

Table 2 indicates that all four distributions demonstrate a satisfactory fit to the data, as the null hypothesis for the K-S test is not rejected for any of the distributions. Among these, the beta distribution emerges as the most effective model, followed by the Kumaraswamy, MBUR, and MBUW distributions. It is pertinent to note that MBUR represents a specific case of MBUW when the parameter b is equal to 2. The beta distribution also exhibits the most favorable values for the AIC, CAIC, and BIC compared to the other distributions. Furthermore, the comparably lower values observed in the K-S test, AD test, and CVM tests for the beta distribution substantiate these findings. It is noteworthy that the variance of the estimators for MBUW is particularly high, resulting in unreliable estimates of the standard error. In contrast, the application of the GMMs and the percentile estimator significantly mitigates the variance, thereby enhancing the estimation of the standard error and facilitating the construction of confidence intervals.

4.3. GMMs and Percentile Estimators. Table 3 illustrates the comparisons between the methods explained in Section 3 for the voter dataset. Methods used for this dataset are illustrated with figures for the comparison between the methods. Figures 6 and 7 show the QQ plot, PP plot, and the fitted PDFs for the voter dataset.

TABLE 1: The descriptive statistics for the voter dataset.

	Minimum	Mean	Standard deviation	Skewness	Kurtosis	25 th quantile	Median	75 th quantile	Maximum
Voter	0.45	0.6911	0.1251	-0.0456	2.2538	0.62	0.68	0.78	0.92

FIGURE 5: Boxplot for voter turnout dataset.

TABLE 2: Statistical indices for the voter dataset (voter turnout, $n = 38$).

	Beta	Kumaraswamy	MBUR	MBUW
Theta	$\alpha = 8.6959$ $\beta = 3.8673$	$\alpha = 5.6224$ $\beta = 4.5073$	0.6832	$\alpha = 0.5509$ $\beta = 1.2779$
Variance	6.4427 2.3588	0.7462 0.9005	0.9005 1.6212	0.0016
Standard error	Standard error for alpha = 2.538 Standard error for beta = 0.9904	Standard error for alpha = 0.8636 Standard error for beta = 1.2732	Standard error for alpha = 0.04	Cannot be estimated Cannot be estimated
AIC	-47.9451	-46.8575	-42.1377	-40.1377
CAIC	-47.6022	-46.5146	-42.0266	-39.7948
BIC	-44.6699	-43.5823	-40.5001	-36.8625
LL	25.9725	25.4287	22.0688	22.0688
K-S	0.0938	0.1048	0.1364	0.1364
H_0	Fail to reject	Fail to reject	Fail to reject	Fail to reject
p value	0.8605	0.7596	0.4401	0.4401
AD	0.2721	0.3464	1.3262	1.3262
CVM	0.0416	0.0559	0.2193	0.2193

5. Discussion

5.1. Ranking of Methods

5.1.1. Relative Rank. The traditional or standard ranks of methods are $1, 2, \dots, m$. This ranking only shows the order of the methods. It fails to depict the exact positions of methods with one another. Reference [46] proposed a new method of ranking, in which each method is given a relative rank, computed to display the relative position of the method. The relative rank is defined in equation (59) as

$$R_i = 1 + \frac{(m-1)(S_i - S_{\min})}{(S_{\max} - S_{\min})}, \quad (59)$$

R_i is the relative rank of method i . S_i is the goodness-of-fit (GOF) statistics obtained by method i . S_{\min} is the minimum of the value of S_i . S_{\max} is the maximum of the value of S_i .

In this ranking system, the best method has a relative rank of 1, and the worst method has the relative rank of m . Ranks of remaining methods are expressed as real numbers between 1 and m . Since the magnitude and not only the

TABLE 3: Comparisons between methods for voter dataset.

	Method 1 = (1st moment & 2 nd moment)	Method 2 = (3 rd moment & 4 th moment)	Method 3 (skewness, log geometric mean)	Method 4 (skewness, log geometric mean)	Method 5 (y ₂₅ = 25 th percentile), (y ₇₅ = 75 th percentile)	Method6 (Galton skewness, Moore kurtosis)
Alpha & (standard error)	0.1374 (0.0520)	0.6172 (0.3494)	0.1609 (0.0344)	0.1793 (0.0371)	0.5492 (0.0559)	0.6811 (0.9519)
Beta & (standard error)	0.3462 (0.0609)	1.2610 (0.6946)	0.3292 (0.0371)	0.3154 (0.0377)	1.2783 (0.1090)	1.385 (1.9678)
AD	1.1204	1.3336	1.3736	1.8384	1.3492	1.9416
CVM	0.1576	0.1920	0.2000	0.2982	0.2252	0.3207
KS	0.1166	0.1516	0.1549	0.1834	0.1382	0.1884
H0	Fail to reject	Fail to reject	Fail to reject	Fail to reject	Fail to reject	Fail to reject
p value for (KS)	0.6434	0.3145	0.2905	0.1366	0.4239	0.1179
Galton skewness	—	—	—	—	—	0.25
Moore kurtosis	—	—	—	—	—	1.5625
Significance of alpha parameter (p value)	2.6427 (0.012)	1.7667 (0.0855)	4.6802 (< 0.001)	4.8350 (< 0.001)	9.8260 (< 0.001)	0.7155 (0.4788)
Significance of beta parameter (p value)	5.6889 (< 0.001)	1.8154 (0.0776)	8.8811 (< 0.001)	8.3745 (< 0.001)	11.7247 (< 0.001)	0.7038 (0.4859)
M1 (1 st sample moment), M2 (2 nd sample moment)	0.6911, 0.4928	—	—	—	—	—
M3 (3 rd sample moment), M4 (4 th sample moment)	—	0.3615, 0.272	—	—	—	—
Mean Log (y)	—	—	-0.3862	-0.3862	—	—
Y _{25v25th} percentile), Y _{75 (75th percentile)}	—	—	—	—	0.62, 0.78	—
Sample skewness for 3 rd method	—	—	0.25	—	—	—
Sample skewness for 4 th method	—	—	—	0.1098	—	—
Determinant	5.7006e - 06	0.0508	9e - 07	1e - 06	0.00003	3.1713
Trace	0.0064	0.6045	0.0026	0.0028	0.015	4.7785

order of S_i is taken into account, this ranking system should provide more information than the traditional ordinal rank. This system was used by [45, 47], who used the system, and for each method, the relative ranks were summed across the different GOF statistics to ascertain the best point for the estimator.

The system of relative rank, using the approach proposed by Ogana, that is, to sum across the 3 GOF statistics, was utilized to order the method for the voter dataset. Table 4 shows a comparison among the methods, showing a good fit as proposed by this relative rank system.

5.1.2. Delta Method. Using the delta method [48] to estimate the variance-covariance of each method encountered a lot of problems. The variance of each method is defined according to the delta method as $n^{-1}K_g(\theta)VK_g'(\theta)$. V matrix is the: $[J'(\theta^{(a)})J(\theta^{(a)}) + \lambda^{(a)}I^{(a)}]^{-1}$ obtained from the LM algorithm used to estimate the parameters, and the K matrix is the partial derivatives of the functions of the parameters with respect to each parameter within the equations used in each method or the Jacobian used in the LM algorithm. Using

delta in this sense yields the variance-covariance matrix of the statistics or the functions of the parameters in each method.

5.2. Discussion of the Results. The analysis of the voter dataset indicates that the MBUW distribution fits the data well. Although it ranks fourth compared to three other distributions based on comparison tools, the MBUW remains a novel distribution with notable advantages. It is derived from the two-parameter Weibull distribution and features a closed form for both the CDF and the quantile function. This characteristic makes it applicable in various fields, including reliability studies, time-to-event studies, and regression analysis involving a variable that follows the MBUW distribution in relation to covariates. It is important to emphasize that it has some advantages over the beta distribution and Kumaraswamy distribution. It has a closed explicit quantile function in comparison with the beta distribution which requires a special function. It has an explicit function for the mean and variance in comparison to the Kumaraswamy distribution which requires a special

FIGURE 6: QQ plot and PP plot for the voter turnout dataset.

function. These advantages make the distribution a good candidate for a quantile regression model of the response variable with the covariates and for mean-based generalized regression models.

In the analysis, MLE was employed. The optimization technique used was the derivative-free Nelder–Mead simplex algorithm. It is important to note that the variances were very large, complicating the estimation of standard errors and rendering them unreliable. Additionally, the variance–covariance matrices displayed near singularity, an issue that could be addressed using a more stable optimization method. This problem may be resolved through modified MLE or alternative estimation methods, such as the GMMs and its variants. Modifications to the percentile estimators could also prove beneficial.

The GMM and percentile methods were utilized to analyze the data. The author employed MLE estimators as initial guesses for some of these methods, which resulted in a significant reduction in the variance compared to the MLE method.

GMM variants and percentile estimators demonstrated a good fit, as indicated by a small K-S test value and a significant p value supporting the model’s fitness. Furthermore, the significance of each parameter was notably high in relation to the t -test because the variance of estimator, as will

be discussed, was significantly reduced. Method 1, Method 2, Method 3, Method 4, Method 5, and Method 6 display a good fit for the voter dataset. Table 5 shows the types of the variance–covariance matrix of the estimated parameters and of the functions of the estimated parameters. The first column is the approximate covariance matrix after running the LM algorithm with a small regularization or damping factor. The second column depicts the approximate covariance matrix obtained after applying the delta method $(n^{-1}K_g(\theta)VK_g'(\theta))$ as described in Section 5.1.2. The third column describes the covariance matrix of the moments or quantiles according to an exact formula as in moment-based statistics, quantile-based statistics, or after resampling distribution as in mixed quantile and moment-based statistics. The fourth column demonstrates $\text{var}(\hat{\theta}) = [[g'(\theta_0)]^T (\text{var}[g(\hat{\theta})])^{-1} g'(\theta_0) + \lambda I]^{-1}$ as described in the first method, which is an approximated covariance matrix after applying a small regularization factor to decrease the condition number of the sensitivity matrix $[g'(\theta_0)]^T (\text{var}[g(\hat{\theta})])^{-1} g'(\theta_0)$. Table 6 shows the matrix of the first derivative of each of the statistics with respect to the parameters used in each method evaluated at the estimated parameters (Jacobian matrix). The Jacobian matrices are ill-conditioned. Table 3 demonstrates the values of the

FIGURE 7: PDF after using different methods of estimation for the voter turnout dataset.

estimated parameters and GOF results acquired after running LM for different methods. The standard errors, the significance of the estimated parameters, the determinant, and the trace reported in Table 3 are obtained from utilizing the covariance matrix in the fourth column of Table 5.

Analysis of the types of variances in Table 5 shows that the matrices (first column) obtained from the LM have a large condition number, and this is due to the small entries in the Jacobian matrices in each method, as shown in Table 6. This influences the information matrix that becomes nearly singular, and so the inverse of this matrix becomes difficult. So the addition of a small regularization factor enhances the procedure of estimation. But the problem is still there when using the delta method to estimate the variance of the statistics. Using the delta method (second column) as described in Section 5.1.2 ($n^{-1}K_g(\theta)VK_g'(\theta)$) gives matrices with even larger condition numbers except for the third and fourth moment-based statistics (second method). The quantile-based statistics or mixed quantile-zero moment-based statistics utilizing the 25th and 75th in their definitions have very large negative condition numbers, as shown in Methods 3, 5, and 6 (second column). The matrices in the third column, denoting the covariance of the sample statistics applying the exact formula (as described in each method if feasible) or bootstrap resampling from the data, have small condition numbers. The

matrices obtained from the resampling procedure (like Method 3 and Method 4) have larger numbers than the matrices gained from the methods using the exact formula for calculating the statistics covariance matrix. Methods 3 and 4 are mixed quantile and moment-based statistics. While the other methods use either moment-based or quantile-based statistics. The covariance matrices of estimated parameters in the fourth column have very large condition number, and this reflects the high correlation between the parameters, and it is due to the effect of the ill-conditioned Jacobian. This can be solved by adding a small regularization factor to this matrix $[g'(\theta_0)]^T (\text{var}[g(\hat{\theta})])^{-1} g'(\theta_0)$ as described in each method, so the variance of the estimated parameter will not explode. The regularization factor can be chosen according to the desired condition number. Here, in the paper, the author used a condition number equal to 5. The matrices in the last column were used to calculate the standard error, to determine the significance of each of the parameter, and to compute the determinant and the trace for comparison among the methods. Estimators with low values of determinant and trace are better and more efficient than the others. So the methods in Table 3 can be ranked according to the values of the determinant and trace. Relative ranking incorporates the MLE because it mainly depends on the GOF statistics rather than the covariance matrix of the estimated

TABLE 4: Comparison between methods after fitting the voter dataset using relative ranking procedure.

Method name	Number of method	Voter			Sum across the 3 goodness of fit	Ascending sort of the sum from min to max	The corresponding method ranked from the best to the worst
		AD	CVM	KS			
M1 & M2 (1 st moment & 2 nd moment) based method	1	1.1204	0.1579	0.1166			
M3 & M4 (3 rd moment & 4 th moment) based method	2	1.3336	0.192	0.1516			
Skewness-based on quartile & log geometric mean base method	3	1.3736	0.2000	0.1549			
Skewness-based on decile & log geometric mean based method	4	1.8384	0.2982	0.1834			
25 th percentile & 75 th percentile	5	1.3492	0.2252	0.1382			
Galton & Moore based method	6	1.9416	0.3207	0.1884			
MLE	7	1.3262	0.2193	0.1364			
Minimum of the goodness of fit		1.1204	0.1579	0.1166			
Maximum of the goodness of fit		1.9416	0.3207	0.1884			
$R_i = 1 + (m - 1)(S_i - S_{\min}) / (S_{\max} - S_{\min})$	$R_{(1)}$	1	1	1	3	3	Method 1
Where: m = number of methods	$R_{(2)}$	2.2981	2.0473	3.4373	7.7827	7.5176	Method 7
S_i is the value of goodness of fit of the method	$R_{(3)}$	2.5416	2.2929	3.6671	8.5017	7.7827	Method 2
S_{\min} is the minimum value of S_i	$R_{(4)}$	5.3716	5.3089	5.6518	16.3324	7.9642	Method 5
S_{\max} is the maximum value of S_i	$R_{(5)}$	2.393	3.0669	2.5042	7.9642	8.5017	Method 3
	$R_{(6)}$	6	6	6	18	16.3324	Method 4
	$R_{(7)}$	2.2530	2.8857	2.3788	7.5176	18	Method 6

Note: For each method that demonstrates a good fit, calculate the AD, CVM, and KS values. Evaluate the minimum and maximum values for each of these tests. Next, apply the formula from equation (59). Sum the results obtained from this equation for each method. Finally, sort the results from the smallest to the largest, which corresponds to ranking from the best to the worst, as illustrated for the voter dataset in the above table.

TABLE 5: Types of variances for the estimated parameters and the estimated functions of parameters.

	Covariance matrix of the estimated parameters obtained from LM equation (17)	Covariance matrix from delta applied to LM covariance matrix section 4.1.2	Covariance matrix of the statistics from exact formula or resampling Appendix A	Covariance matrix of the estimated parameter using a regularizing factor according to a specified chosen condition number
Method 1	$\begin{bmatrix} 383.3523 & 485.7652 \\ 485.7652 & 617.3376 \end{bmatrix}$ $C = 1449.4$	$\begin{bmatrix} 0.0104 & 0.0129 \\ 0.0129 & 0.0159 \end{bmatrix}$ $C = \text{inf}$	$\begin{bmatrix} 0.0008 & 0.001 \\ 0.001 & 0.0013 \end{bmatrix}$ $C = 1.2967$	$\begin{bmatrix} 0.0027 & 0.0021 \\ 0.0021 & 0.0037 \end{bmatrix}$ $C_{\text{before}} = -1.3181e + 16$
Method 2	$\begin{bmatrix} 6.6951 & 22.0378 \\ 22.0378 & 94.7949 \end{bmatrix}$ $C = 67.1144$	$\begin{bmatrix} 0.0141 & 0.0129 \\ 0.0129 & 0.0118 \end{bmatrix}$ $C = 1.0941$	$\begin{bmatrix} 0.0548 & 0.0527 \\ 0.0527 & 0.0514 \end{bmatrix}$ $C = 1.0322$	$\begin{bmatrix} 0.1221 & 0.0902 \\ 0.0902 & 0.4825 \end{bmatrix}$ $C_{\text{before}} = 1.4303e + 17$
Method 3	$\begin{bmatrix} 44.7 & 49.3803 \\ 49.3803 & 55.9058 \end{bmatrix}$ $C = 165.0713$	$\begin{bmatrix} 0.0011 & -0.0053 \\ -0.0053 & 0.0250 \end{bmatrix}$ $C = -7.5391e + 15$	$\begin{bmatrix} 0.0648 & 0.0019 \\ 0.0019 & 0.0009 \end{bmatrix}$ $C = 76.7363$	$\begin{bmatrix} 0.0012 & 0.0008 \\ 0.0008 & 0.0014 \end{bmatrix}$ $C_{\text{before}} = -1.6519e + 16$
Method 4	$\begin{bmatrix} 49.1486 & 49.6844 \\ 49.6844 & 51.4558 \end{bmatrix}$ $C = 165.4586$	$\begin{bmatrix} 0.0036 & -0.0090 \\ -0.0090 & 0.0226 \end{bmatrix}$ $C = 7.5392e + 15$	$\begin{bmatrix} 0.0204 & -0.0004 \\ -0.0004 & 0.0008 \end{bmatrix}$ $C = 24.9884$	$\begin{bmatrix} 0.0014 & 0.0009 \\ 0.0009 & 0.0014 \end{bmatrix}$ $C_{\text{before}} = 3.0227e + 16$
Method 5	$\begin{bmatrix} 63.5343 & 241.1174 \\ 241.1174 & 937.9181 \end{bmatrix}$ $C = 688.5453$	$\begin{bmatrix} 0.0211 & 0.0104 \\ 0.0104 & 0.0052 \end{bmatrix}$ $C = -3.0296e + 16$	$\begin{bmatrix} 0.0020 & 0.0005 \\ 0.0005 & 0.0009 \end{bmatrix}$ $C = 2.8622$	$\begin{bmatrix} 0.0031 & 0.0024 \\ 0.0024 & 0.0119 \end{bmatrix}$ $C_{\text{before}} = -9.0007e + 16$
Method 6	$\begin{bmatrix} 47.6598 & 179.8608 \\ 179.8608 & 966.0311 \end{bmatrix}$ $C = 73.0410$	$\begin{bmatrix} 0.0169 & -0.0124 \\ -0.0124 & 0.0091 \end{bmatrix}$ $C = -2.9925e + 16$	$\begin{bmatrix} 0.1189 & 0.0251 \\ 0.0251 & 0.0738 \end{bmatrix}$ $C = 2.0776$	$\begin{bmatrix} 0.9061 & 0.5809 \\ 0.5809 & 3.8723 \end{bmatrix}$ $C_{\text{before}} = 1.4476e + 17$

Note: C before denotes condition number before adding the regularization factor. And C denotes condition number.

TABLE 6: The Jacobian matrix for each method.

	Method 1	Method 2	Method 3
Jacobian matrix	$\begin{bmatrix} -0.5941 & 0.4680 \\ -0.7354 & 0.5793 \end{bmatrix}$ $C = -2.4830e - 13$	$\begin{bmatrix} -0.5841 & 0.1380 \\ -0.5339 & 0.1261 \end{bmatrix}$ $C = 0$	$\begin{bmatrix} 0.1995 & -0.1781 \\ -0.9344 & 0.8344 \end{bmatrix}$ $C = 4.6559e + 15$
	Method 4	Method 5	Method 6
Jacobian matrix	$\begin{bmatrix} 0.3386 & -0.3309 \\ -0.8525 & 0.8329 \end{bmatrix}$ $C = -3.5174e + 15$	$\begin{bmatrix} -0.7199 & 0.1854 \\ -0.3557 & 0.0916 \end{bmatrix}$ $C = -2.2087e - 17$	$\begin{bmatrix} 0.2126 & -0.0401 \\ -0.1561 & 0.0295 \end{bmatrix}$ $C = -2.1803e + 15$

parameters. Using the determinant or the trace as in Table 3 ranks the methods from the best to the worst according to the method, from the lowest determinant to the highest one as follows: the best method is method 3, followed by Method 4 then Method 1, Method 5, Method 2, and lastly Method 6, while the relative ranks order the methods as shown in Table 4.

6. Conclusion

This new distribution effectively addresses the limitations of the Weibull distribution, particularly its absence of bathtub and unimodal shapes. Furthermore, it is defined over the unit interval, making it ideal for fitting proportions and ratios. With a well-defined quantile function, this distribution is fully compatible with parametric quantile regression, enabling conditioning on the median or any other quantile. This is a significant advantage, as the mean is often an inadequate measure of central tendency for highly skewed distributions. The closed-form expression of its mean and variance makes it a good candidate for the mean-based regression model if needed. The innovative approach utilizing the GMM method and percentile estimator significantly enhances the parameter estimation process for the MBUW distribution. It computes both parameters simultaneously by solving differential equations using iterative techniques such as the LM algorithm. It provides more stable and reliable estimates with reduced variance. These estimators serve as robust initial guesses for other methods requiring numerical computations.

Choosing between the statistics to construct the system of equations is perplexing. The statistics are preferable to exhibit weak correlation to avoid the problems of ill-conditioning, unidentifiability, and hence very large variance. The correlation between statistics may be data-driven

for which bootstrap resampling may not ameliorate it. Some data may drive the chosen statistics to be highly correlated rather than other data. This is shown in the third column of Table 5. So studying the data prior to constructing the system of statistics is a good practice that may save a lot of time. In Methods 3 and 4, resampling revealed the covariance matrix with a considerably larger condition number than the condition number of other statistics.

6.1. Future Work. Estimating the parameters of the MBUW distribution can be challenging, especially when both parameters are unknown, because they tend to be highly correlated. One effective approach is to use Bayesian statistics. Alternative methods include modified MLE and variants of the GMMs that incorporate kurtosis and the log of the geometric mean, or the Fisher coefficient of skewness and kurtosis, which the author did not utilize. The problems of ill conditioning, strength of identification, and correlation between statistics are major problems to be faced when constructing the system of statistics. The correlation between statistics is mainly data-driven rather than statistics-driven. The chosen moment-based statistics, quantile-based statistics, or mixed quantile-moment-based statistics are one of the most important challenges in the estimation procedure in conjunction with the optimization algorithm. Other techniques that can be explored include least squares, weighted least squares, and the maximum product of spacing method.

Appendix A

$\text{var}(\mu'_r) = (\mu'_{2r} - (\mu'_r)^2)/n$ and $\text{cov}(\mu'_r, \mu'_q) = (\mu'_{r+q} - \mu'_r \mu'_q)/n$, the numerator is only shown

$$\text{var}(\mu'_1) = \mu'_2 - (\mu'_1)^2 = \frac{6}{(2 + 2\alpha^\beta)(3 + 2\alpha^\beta)} - \left(\frac{6}{(2 + \alpha^\beta)(3 + \alpha^\beta)} \right)^2, \tag{A.1}$$

$$\text{var}(\mu'_2) = \mu'_4 - (\mu'_2)^2 = \frac{6}{(2 + 4\alpha^\beta)(3 + 4\alpha^\beta)} - \left(\frac{6}{(2 + 2\alpha^\beta)(3 + 2\alpha^\beta)} \right)^2, \tag{A.2}$$

$$\text{var}(\mu'_3) = \mu'_6 - (\mu'_3)^2 = \frac{6}{(2 + 6\alpha^\beta)(3 + 6\alpha^\beta)} - \left(\frac{6}{(2 + 3\alpha^\beta)(3 + 3\alpha^\beta)} \right)^2, \tag{A.3}$$

$$\text{var}(\mu'_4) = \mu'_8 - (\mu'_4)^2 = \frac{6}{(2 + 8\alpha^\beta)(3 + 8\alpha^\beta)} - \left(\frac{6}{(2 + 4\alpha^\beta)(3 + 4\alpha^\beta)} \right)^2, \tag{A.5}$$

$$\text{cov}(\mu'_1, \mu'_2) = \mu'_3 - \mu'_1 \mu'_2, \text{cov}(\mu'_3, \mu'_4) = \mu'_7 - \mu'_3 \mu'_4, \tag{A.6}$$

$$\text{var}[\widehat{Q}(1/8)] = \frac{p(1-p)}{nf^2(\widehat{Q}(p))}, \text{ where } p = 0.125 \text{ and } f(\widehat{Q}(p)), \tag{A.7}$$

$$\text{cov}[\hat{Q}(1/8), \hat{Q}(7/8)] = \frac{\min(0.125, 0.875) - (0.125)(0.875)}{nf(\hat{Q}(0.125))f(\hat{Q}(0.875))}. \quad (\text{A.8})$$

$$= \begin{bmatrix} \text{var}[\hat{Q}(\frac{1}{8})] & \text{cov}[\hat{Q}(\frac{1}{8}), \hat{Q}(\frac{2}{8})] & \text{cov}[\hat{Q}(\frac{1}{8}), \hat{Q}(\frac{3}{8})] & \text{cov}[\hat{Q}(\frac{1}{8}), \hat{Q}(\frac{4}{8})] & \text{cov}[\hat{Q}(\frac{1}{8}), \hat{Q}(\frac{5}{8})] & \text{cov}[\hat{Q}(\frac{1}{8}), \hat{Q}(\frac{6}{8})] & \text{cov}[\hat{Q}(\frac{1}{8}), \hat{Q}(\frac{7}{8})] \\ & \text{var}[\hat{Q}(\frac{2}{8})] & \text{cov}[\hat{Q}(\frac{2}{8}), \hat{Q}(\frac{3}{8})] & \text{cov}[\hat{Q}(\frac{2}{8}), \hat{Q}(\frac{4}{8})] & \text{cov}[\hat{Q}(\frac{2}{8}), \hat{Q}(\frac{5}{8})] & \text{cov}[\hat{Q}(\frac{2}{8}), \hat{Q}(\frac{6}{8})] & \text{cov}[\hat{Q}(\frac{2}{8}), \hat{Q}(\frac{7}{8})] \\ & & \text{var}[\hat{Q}(\frac{3}{8})] & \text{cov}[\hat{Q}(\frac{3}{8}), \hat{Q}(\frac{4}{8})] & \text{cov}[\hat{Q}(\frac{3}{8}), \hat{Q}(\frac{5}{8})] & \text{cov}[\hat{Q}(\frac{3}{8}), \hat{Q}(\frac{6}{8})] & \text{cov}[\hat{Q}(\frac{3}{8}), \hat{Q}(\frac{7}{8})] \\ & & & \text{var}[\hat{Q}(\frac{4}{8})] & \text{cov}[\hat{Q}(\frac{4}{8}), \hat{Q}(\frac{5}{8})] & \text{cov}[\hat{Q}(\frac{4}{8}), \hat{Q}(\frac{6}{8})] & \text{cov}[\hat{Q}(\frac{4}{8}), \hat{Q}(\frac{7}{8})] \\ & & & & \text{var}[\hat{Q}(\frac{5}{8})] & \text{cov}[\hat{Q}(\frac{5}{8}), \hat{Q}(\frac{6}{8})] & \text{cov}[\hat{Q}(\frac{5}{8}), \hat{Q}(\frac{7}{8})] \\ & & & & & \text{var}[\hat{Q}(\frac{6}{8})] & \text{cov}[\hat{Q}(\frac{6}{8}), \hat{Q}(\frac{7}{8})] \\ & & & & & & \text{var}[\hat{Q}(\frac{7}{8})] \end{bmatrix}. \quad (\text{A.9})$$

The same is applicable to other entries.

$\text{var}(\hat{Q})$ is a symmetrical matrix; upper off-diagonal elements are only shown.

Data Availability Statement

Data sharing is not applicable to this article as no new data were created or analyzed in this study.

Ethics Statement

The author has nothing to report.

Consent

The author has nothing to report.

Disclosure

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Conflicts of Interest

The author declares no conflicts of interest.

Author Contributions

Iman M. Attia carried out the conceptualization by formulating the goals and aims of the research article; formal analysis by applying the statistical, mathematical, and computational techniques to synthesize and analyze the real data; and carried out the methodology by creating the model, software programming and implementation, supervision, writing, drafting, editing, preparation, and creation of the presenting work.

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